

The Effect of Five Finger Hypnosis in Reducing Anxiety Levels on Adolescents During the Covid-19 Pandemic

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Abstract:- COVID-19 is a pandemic in Indonesia and has spread to almost all countries, so it has been called a global pandemic. This pandemic outbreak has a negative impact on physical and psychological health, causing uncontrollable anxiety in individuals or society. Covid-19 significantly affects the self-concept of every teenager, and psychological changes are marked by changing attitudes, feelings, and emotions. Efforts to deal with Covid-19 are not only focused on physical health but also psychological and social. One of them is by giving five-finger hypnosis therapy. This research method uses a *pre-experimental research design* in one group (*One group Pre-Test Post-Test Design*), where a pre-test is carried out on the respondents before being given post-test treatment. The research location was conducted at Universitas Adiwangsa Jambi in 2021. The research sample was 30 samples, with primary data collection by distributing the Hamilton Branches Scale for Anxiety questionnaire (HRS-A). Analysis used *Paired Sample t-Test*. The results showed that the P-value = 0.000 where the p-value < ($\alpha = 0.05$), so it can be concluded that there is a difference in the value of the pre-test and post-test behavior measurements. Furthermore, there is a significant effect of giving five-finger hypnosis therapy to decrease anxiety levels.

Keywords:- Covid-19; Five Finger Hypnosis; Anxiety Level; Teenagers.

I. INTRODUCTION

Currently, COVID-19 is a pandemic in Indonesia and has spread to almost all countries, so it has been called a global pandemic. This pandemic outbreak has a negative impact on physical and psychological health, causing uncontrollable anxiety in individuals or society [1].

In Indonesia, the number of anxiety continues to increase every year, and it is estimated that 20% of the world's population and as many as 47.7% of adolescents feel anxious [2]. According to Sadock et al., anxiety is a response to certain threatening situations and is a normal thing to happen. Anxiety begins with a threatening situation as a dangerous stimulus (stressor). Anxiety can make a person more aware of a threat at a certain level because if the threat is considered harmless, then a person will not do self-defense. In connection with facing the Covid-19 pandemic, anxiety needs to be managed properly so that it continues to provide awareness but does not cause excessive panic or lead to worse mental health disorders [3].

Every day the number of positive victims of Covid-19 is still increasing. This virus attacks everyone regardless of gender and age [4]. No exception during the transition period or the transition period due to biological and psychological growth, development, and changes, Covid-19 greatly affects young people's self-concept, and psychological changes are marked by changing attitudes, feelings, and emotions. The Covid-19 that occurs will add to the storm and stress on teenagers, and it can even cause anxiety. Therefore, efforts to deal with Covid-19 are focused on physical health and psychological and social. One of them is giving teenagers five-finger hypnosis therapy to reduce anxiety levels due to the Covid-19 pandemic [5].

Five-finger hypnosis is a form of self-hypnosis that can cause a high relaxation effect so that it will reduce tension and stress from one's mind. Giving. The research results conducted by Jenita, showed that five-finger hypnosis is a proven and very effective method for reducing anxiety [6]. According to Retno, about the effect of five-finger hypnosis therapy techniques to reduce anxiety in students who are compiling a thesis, it shows that measurements before treatment obtained moderate anxiety results as many as 18 people (100%), and after receiving treatment, it became 15 people (83.3%) experienced mild anxiety and three people (16.7%) experienced moderate anxiety [7].

Based on a survey of initial data from ten adolescents, seven adolescents (70%) experienced excessive fear and worry, felt unable to relax and be comfortable, experienced sleep disturbances, and were overly aware of the COVID-19 pandemic. Meanwhile, three adolescents (30%) said they were worried because they couldn't go to school, as usual, couldn't meet and go with friends. From the above phenomenon, researchers are interested in researching "The Effect of Five Finger Hypnosis in reducing anxiety levels on adolescents during the Covid-19 Pandemic Period."

II. RESEARCH METHOD

This research used pre-experimentation in one group (*One group Pre-Test Post-Test Design*). Respondents were pre-tested before receiving treatment, and respondents were given post-tests after being given treatment [8]. The treatment for adolescents is in Five Finger Hypnosis for approximately 10 minutes in 1 meeting.

This research was conducted at Universitas Adiwangsa Jambi, and the research was carried out in 2021. The research sample was 30 adolescents who were in the Universitas Adiwangsa Jambi environment. The sampling technique used is the non-probability method, the type of purposive sampling is based on the calculation of the sample size. Data collection with primary data is obtained directly by distributing questionnaires (HRS-A) Hamilton Branch Scale for Anxiety. This measuring instrument consists of 14 symptom questions, and each symptom question is rated between 0-4, which means:

- 0 = none (no symptoms)
- 1 = mild symptom (one symptom from the available options)
- 2 = moderate symptoms (half of the symptoms present)
- 3 = severe symptoms (more than half of the symptoms present)
- 4 = very severe symptoms (all symptoms present).

Analysis of the data used in this study is the *Paired Sample t-Test*. The paired t-test is used to determine the difference between the pre-test and post-test scores for each group.

III. RESULT AND DISCUSSION

A. Univariate Analysis

Table 1. Characteristics of Respondents

Variable	Frequency	%
Gender		
Male	7	23.3
Female	23	76.7
Age		
19	8	26.7
20	14	46.7
21	8	26.7
Pre-Test Anxiety Level		
No Symptoms	3	10.0
Mild Symptoms	5	16.7
Moderate Symptoms	16	53.3
Severe Symptoms	6	20.0
Very Severe Symptoms	0	0
Post-Test Anxiety Level		
No Symptoms	16	53.3
Mild Symptoms	10	33.3
Moderate Symptoms	4	13.3
Severe Symptoms	0	0
Very Severe Symptoms	0	0
N	30	100

Source: Primary Data, 2021

Table 3.1 shows that the number of respondents is dominated by female students (76.7%) compared to male students (23.3%). In the age of respondents, the age range is between 19-21 years, with the average respondent being 20 years old (46.7%) compared to 19 years (26.7%) and 21 years

(26.7%). Respondents' anxiety level before treatment/pre-test showed no symptoms 10%, mild symptoms 16.7%, moderate symptoms 53.3%, severe symptoms 20%, and no one experienced very severe symptoms. While the level of anxiety after treatment/post-test showed no symptoms 53.3%, mild symptoms 33.3%, moderate symptoms 13.3%, and no severe or very severe symptoms.

B. Bivariate Analysis

➤ Paired t Test

Paired t test was used to determine the difference between the pre-test and post-test scores for each group.

Table 2. Results of Differences in Pre-Post Test Anxiety Levels Before and After Five Finger Hypnosis

	N	Mean	SD	t	Sig (tailed)
Pretest	30	1.83	0.874	10.790	0.000
Posttest		0.60	0.724		

Based on Table 3.2, it is known that the average anxiety in students before treatment/pre-test was 1.83, and at the post-test stage after being given treatment decreased to 0.60. The results obtained a p-value of 0.000 ($p > 0.05$) which means that there are differences in anxiety in students before and after treatment.

❖ Discussion

A. Characteristics of Respondents

Characteristics of respondents in this study were seven male respondents (23.3%) and 23 female respondents (76.7%) with an age range of 19-21 years, where the average age of respondents was 20 years (46.7%), in terms of this large number of respondents also affects the level of anxiety. In this study, most respondents were female, and the average respondent's anxiety before being given the intervention was anxiety with moderate symptoms.

Kaplan & Sadock, stated that women experience anxiety more often than men. Women have higher levels of anxiety than men, and this is because women are more sensitive to emotions, which in turn affects their feelings of anxiety [9]. The results of this study are also in line with the results of research conducted by Hastuti, R. Y & Arumsari, A, which states that most respondents who experience anxiety are women [10]. Prawirohusodo, stated that young people experience more stress and anxiety because the coping mechanisms have not been fully formed, so difficulties in making decisions continue with anxiety [11].

Respondents' anxiety level before treatment/pre-test showed no symptoms 10%, mild symptoms 16.7%, moderate symptoms 53.3%, severe symptoms 20%, and no one experienced very severe symptoms. While the level of anxiety after treatment/post-test showed no symptoms 53.3%, mild symptoms 33.3%, moderate symptoms 13.3%, and no severe or very severe symptoms. Based on the results before and after treatment, it showed a decrease in the results of each symptom, where after five-finger hypnosis. Furthermore, no more

students experienced severe or very severe symptoms, and the average results showed no more symptoms.

B. The Effect of Five Finger Hypnosis in Reducing Anxiety Levels

Based on Table 3.2, it is shown that the average anxiety of students before the intervention was 1.83 (moderate anxiety) with a standard deviation of 0.874. Meanwhile, after being given the intervention, the average value of student anxiety dropped to 0.60 (mild anxiety) with a standard deviation of 0.724, with a P-value = 0.000 where $p\text{-value} < (\alpha = 0.05)$, so it can be concluded that there is a difference in the value of the pretest behavior measurement and posttest. With these results, it means that H_0 is rejected and H_a is accepted, so it can be concluded that there is a significant effect of giving five-finger hypnosis therapy to decrease anxiety levels.

Anxiety is a feeling of worry as if something bad will happen and feeling uncomfortable as if there is a threat accompanied by physical symptoms such as heart palpitations, cold sweats, and shaking hands [12].

Anxiety is a worry that is unclear and widespread, non-specific in nature, and is described as a General Adaptation Syndrome. General Adaptation Syndrome is a defense response to stress from the whole body. There are three phases of the stress reaction, namely the first phase of the alarm reaction (alert) phase, which is the body's initial response to stress by activating the sympathetic nervous system and the body's hormone system, such as catecholamine, epinephrine, norepinephrine, glucocorticoids, cortisol, and cortisone. The second stage of resistance (defense reaction) is the body's response to stressors by using the body's abilities so that psychic and somatic symptoms arise. Finally, the third stage of exhaustion (fatigue/fatigue) is a response or symptoms that arise due to stressors such as headaches, mental disorders, coronary artery disease, hypertension, dyspepsia (gastrointestinal complaints), depression, anxiety, frigidity, and impotence [13].

Management of anxiety (anxiety) can be done using pharmacological therapy and non-pharmacological therapy. Pharmacological therapy includes anxiolytic, while non-pharmacological therapy with psychotherapy, cognitive therapy, laughter therapy, relaxation, and five-finger hypnosis. One way that can reduce anxiety is five-finger hypnosis. Five-finger hypnosis gives treatment in a relaxed state, focusing on the image or memory created while touching the five fingers in sequence by imagining memories. The benefits of five-finger hypnosis are increasing enthusiasm, creating peace in the heart, and reducing tension [11].

The results of this study are in line with Hastuti's research regarding the effect of five-finger hypnosis therapy to reduce anxiety in students who are writing a thesis, with the p-value obtained at 0.000 ($p > 0.05$). This means that there were differences anxiety on adolescents before and after treatment [10].

A study conducted by Dekawaty, stated the effect of five-finger hypnosis therapy on student anxiety facing thesis, with a p-value < 0.05 . This shows a significant difference in the average anxiety of students facing the thesis before and after being given the five-finger hypnosis intervention [14].

Retno's Pre-Experimental Research is also in line with the results of this study, and she used the One group Pre test - Post test research design approach, which aims to determine the effect of five-finger hypnosis therapy to reduce anxiety in students, it was concluded that there was a significant effect of giving hypnosis therapy five fingers with a decrease in anxiety in students [7].

Five-finger hypnosis is a form of self-hypnosis that can cause a high relaxation effect, so it will reduce tension and stress from one's mind so that the provision of five-finger hypnosis is very influential on reducing student anxiety levels, according to research by Kamilatur, which states that adolescents who are given hypnosis, her thought waves enter alpha waves with a frequency of 7-14 hertz or deeper into theta waves with a frequency of 4-7 hertz. When the mind enters this wave, students produce natural endorphins that produce a comfortable sensation. In this hypnotic state, the body's metabolic system becomes much better, and the body is free from tension [15].

IV. CONCLUSION

Handling anxiety in adolescents needs to be considered the negative impacts that will arise. One of the non-pharmacological techniques to overcome anxiety is the five-finger hypnosis method. This method is very practical because it only requires concentration and awareness of the individual who does it. Besides, this method is very affordable. It also supported by the results of this study, where there was an influence on the level of anxiety before and after being treated with the five-finger hypnosis method.

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